

CONFLICTING PROFESSIONAL PRIORITIES IN ELT: TRAINEE-TEACHERS', MENTORS' AND UNIVERSITY INSTRUCTORS' PERSPECTIVES

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Abstract

The paper focuses on the possible reasons for the appearance of conflicting professional priorities during school-based internship from the perspective of the three major agents in the English language classrooms: trainees, mentors, and university instructors. The discussion is based on the results of a survey conducted among 23 BA teacher trainees, and 27 adult re-trainee teachers enrolled in a teacher qualification course at a Bulgarian state university, as well as interviews with some of their mentors and two university supervisors. The survey and the interviews targeted aspects of teaching, which potentially provoke conflicting perceptions about teaching, such as the importance of the teaching context (a big town school or a small village school), awareness of learner variables (motivation, first language, proficiency level), preferred approaches to teaching; familiarity with key concepts in modern teaching, and trainees' personal abilities in teaching and reflection.

Keywords: conflicting priorities, internship, trainees, mentors, university instructors

Introduction

There are three important agents in the learning to teach process – the trainees, usually university students in their last year of study; the mentors – experienced school teachers, who work with one or several trainees, and the university instructors, who often combine the role of a lecturer and a supervisor at different stages of initial teacher training. As a rule, during the internship, they should work together towards achieving a common goal – preparing trainees for their future work as teachers, equipped with the professional knowledge and expertise, which is necessary for independent practice and decision making in a variety of educational contexts.

Teacher learning, which is a prerequisite for developing expertise, is nowadays seen as a socialization into the professional thinking and practices of a community of practice – people who share common concerns, problems, interests and goals (Tsui 2009). Teachers' professional identity is closely linked to developing relationships with students and fellow-teachers, establishing rapport with others involved in the educational process, and contributing to its success through one's own personal qualities and efforts. At the same, time cooperation with others helps us understand better our own experiences and opinions (Edge 1992). Moreover, it makes teachers producers, not just consumers, of knowledge and understanding about teaching (Freeman, Johnson 1998; Johnston 2003).

In this context, trainees' opinions on all matters connected to teaching and learning, and on the relevance of the received instruction and help is important for improving their performance quality and relevance. Therefore, trainees should be able to explore their experience of practice in the light of theory. In this process of professional growth mentors have a crucial role in supporting trainees' first attempts at teaching; they are the role models who provide expertise and emotional support to trainees. There are six different processes of influencing trainees in the process of mentor-

ing, which involve influencing by example, by coaching, through practice-focused discussion, through structuring the context, through emotional support, and through devised learning experiences (Calderhead and Shorrock 1997).

The third key agent in the classroom, the supervisor, ensures the continuity between the theoretical preparation of trainees and its implementation in practice. Supervisors support the quality assurance in teaching and trainees' reflection on action as a prerequisite for their learning about teaching. As Chamberlin (2000) points out, the role of the supervisor is now seen in creating an environment that cultivates reflection, exploration, and change. Recent trends in supervision research are driven by the interest in the sources and mechanisms of development.

The conflicting priorities of trainees, mentors and supervisors might be grounded on a variety of factors, some of which are related to their understanding of the relevance of key components of teacher's professional expertise. In the process of establishing their professional identity during the internship, trainees set their priorities which can be contested by the other responsible actors in the classroom – the mentor and the university instructor. Thus, trainees may want to learn how to teach, but might be stressed out due to the unfamiliarity of the context and people. They wish to have good relationships with students, their mentor and the supervisor who assess their teaching. In addition, other variables might come into play, such as trainees' inclination towards dependence or autonomy, and tensions arising in the transition from the safe learning environment of the university to the real world of the classroom.

Mentors and supervisors also have their expectations about the nature of the trainees' preparation and work which result from their already established ideas about the nature of language teaching and learning, and their understanding of professionalism in terms of practitioners' knowledge, skills, and conduct (Troman 1996). Mentors, on the one hand, have supervisory and

advisory functions, supporting trainees' professionalisation process, while on the other hand, they are involved in the high-stake assessment of the trainees. Supervisors want to make sure trainees successfully apply their university preparation to real world learning contexts, and are ready for the challenges of teaching in different educational contexts. They have to make sure that trainees' performance meets the standards for quality teaching. In this respect, a key factor for successful teaching is trainees' familiarity with key concepts in teaching, and the supervisors' willingness to allow deviation from the models of teaching presented in the instruction course. In addition, some possible reasons for conflicting priorities among the three major agents may lie in the internal tensions within each of these groups. For example, not all trainees have the same theoretical preparation, not all mentors are trained to act as mentors, or are equally willing to share their know-how, and not all supervisors have the same in-depth knowledge of the theoretical course if they do not teach it themselves.

The school-based internship is the time when trainees should take full responsibility for the implementation of the planned teaching activities in the lessons. Trainees do not only plan and teach, but also engage in reflection on the effectiveness of their teaching, and receive feedback on their performance. Internship plays a key role in trainees' decision to become teachers, and is one of the best ways of balancing academic learning with the practical skills which are necessary for ensuring success in a chosen field. It provides a supervised learning experience in which trainees can apply their knowledge, develop already acquired skills and build new ones in a real-world setting (Ivanova 2017). In this way they develop their professional identity which affects the roles teachers perform as experts in their subject, as facilitators of students' learning, and as motivators and sources of inspiration for other teachers and students. These roles and the way they are perceived by society are culturally embedded and may differ depending on factors such as school management system in the country, and the degree of responsibility and freedom teachers have. If teachers are prepared in a way that fits with future working conditions in terms of school type or student characteristics, the likelihood of staying in the teaching profession is increased (Goldhaber et al., 2022). In addition, the time spent in schools helps trainees understand the connection between theory and practice and provides them with a practical opportunity to develop an in-depth understanding of the teaching profession and the working conditions in that profession (Parveen & Mirza 2012). At the same time, internship is the time when conflicting professional priorities meet and sometimes clash, revealing different viewpoints, perceptions, expectations and trends in teacher training. The tensions created by this clash have the potential to predetermine trainees' future in the profession, and are the first test for their knowledge and beliefs about teaching and learning.

The study

The possible reasons for the existence and clash of conflicting priorities during the internship were explored through a small-scale study conducted among 23

BA teacher-trainees and 27 adult re-trainees from a state Bulgarian university after the completion of their school-based internship. The study also involved 15 school mentors and 2 university supervisors who worked with these trainees. The aim of the study was to look into trainee-teachers' assessment of the relevance of some key concepts related to teacher's professional expertise, and to compare it to their mentors' and supervisors' opinions and perceptions. There were two tools which were used for obtaining the data:

1. A questionnaire for the trainees with 5 main areas of teacher expertise which they had to rate based on their teaching practice at school. The 5 areas included trainees' familiarity with the context of teaching, the learners and the mentor; the use of activities, techniques and interaction patterns; the key concepts in teaching, and the trainees' personal abilities in teaching. The importance of each area was assessed by means of a five-point Likert scale (1 – not important, 2 – of little importance, 3 – of average importance, 4 – very important, 5 – absolutely essential).

2. Post-internship group discussion with mentors and supervisors using the questionnaire as a prop, aimed at eliciting expectations and insights which reveal potential conflicting priorities of mentors and supervisors to those of the trainees.

The study aimed to provide answers to the following research questions:

- What do trainees expect from the school-based internship? What do they prioritise as important in teaching?
- What do mentors and instructors expect from the trainees? What do they expect to see in class?
- Are there any differences between mentors' and instructors' understanding of teaching?
- What are the important aspects of teaching and how are they prioritised by the three key participants in the internship – trainees, mentors and university instructors?

Results and analysis

The first area which was targeted in the study was **trainees' prior knowledge of learners**. Having information about the learners in advance is fundamental to successful language teaching. A good teacher should be aware of the way different factors, such as the learning environment, native culture and educational traditions, among others, influence the processes of teaching and learning. A major role in the learning process is played by learner characteristics or variables, such as age, proficiency level, aptitude, learning styles, strategies and intelligences. Targeted sub-areas in the study involved: students' social and educational background, their interests and motivation, age-related characteristics (concentration span, learning habits and preferences), mother tongue, proficiency level, class homogeneity.

The results (Fig.1) showed that it is absolutely important for the trainees to know what interests and motivates students in order to make their lessons more appealing and thus make students cooperate and participate in the lessons. Students' proficiency level, and

more specifically if they are mixed-proficiency, followed by age-related characteristics were considered very important. Trainees wanted to know if there are students who need special attention. The least important factors were students' social and educational background and if Bulgarian was their mother tongue, probably because trainees usually find out about it first thing from the mentors. In the interview the mentors said that they preferred to let trainees see and draw their conclusions for themselves, rather than providing them with information in advance. Priority was given to language proficiency and the need for special attention to students with special needs, while important factors such as students' interests, social and educational background, and age-related factors were considered less important. All mentors agreed that it was important for trainees to have some information about the learners,

but not all of them provided this information in advance. For some mentors it was sufficient to let students observe the class for 1 or 2 lessons. Other mentors said they provided information only if they were asked specific questions, not in a structured pre-planned way. The information was related to the class profile as a whole (proficiency level, mixed-ability, first language /bilingualism). They provided information on individual students – whether they needed special attention, had learning difficulties, or created discipline problems. Nobody mentioned learners' social and educational background, students' interests and age-related characteristics, such as concentration span, learning habits and preference. The supervisors mentioned trainees' inability to deal with students with special educational needs, and the fact that the mentors were not of much help, and sometimes preferred to ignore such students.

Fig.1. Importance of having prior knowledge about learners before teaching them

The second area which was investigated as a potential field for a clash of conflicting priorities was **the context of teaching and the mentor's approach**. In addition to focusing on the key features of the target language, and the learner variables which are essential in language acquisition, teachers have to pay close attention to the contexts in which the languages are taught and learnt. Kumaravadivelu (2006; 2012) outlines 3 parameters of post-method pedagogy which are related to context: particularity, practicality, and possibility. Particularity emphasizes local needs, lived experiences, and a critical awareness of local conditions of learning and teaching based on observing and evaluating teaching acts, identifying problems and finding solutions. The context-related sub-areas in the study involved: trainees' familiarity with school requirements, mentor's approach to teaching and managing students, instruction language, feedback, error correction and ICT use.

The results (Fig.2) showed that for the trainees the most important aspects of familiarity with the local context of teaching were the mentors' approach to managing students and the ways of providing feedback and

error correction. However, most mentors didn't discuss these aspects, just warned trainees against drastic deviations from the way classes are usually taught. For the trainees using ICT in teaching and familiarity with school requirements were less important while their mentors made a point of having to teach trainees how to use technology and electronic resources. Trainees also prioritised classroom management as the single most important factor for achieving lesson aims. They felt obliged to follow feedback and error correction models used by the mentor in order to minimise possible conflicts with students. All mentors allowed trainees to observe them but the number of observed classes varied from 1 to 4 depending on the number of different classes trainees had to teach. Only 2 mentors mentioned school regulations, emphasising that trainees are not allowed to expel misbehaving students. In general there were no complaints about discipline problem because the mentors were always present when trainees taught the classes. However, three mentors said they had to intervene to solve discipline problems, but in all three cases the reason was trainees' inadequate preparation or reaction to students' questions. Most of the mentors

said that they did not discuss their approach to teaching and managing classes with trainees. They thought it was sufficient to let trainees observe them. They only made suggestions about teaching when the trainees did things that mentors disapproved of or have never before

done with their students. Supervisors emphasised the role of mentors in showing trainees how to use technology, and the insufficient quality mentor feedback for trainees' learning.

Fig.2. Context of teaching and mentor's approach

The third area focused on the **use of activities, techniques and interaction patterns** which are considered the building blocks of the lesson, broadly described as "something that learners do that involves them using the language to achieve some specific outcome" (Scrivener 2011: 37). Special attention was paid to activities and techniques which tend to be neglected by Bulgarian teachers, but which are emphasised in the methodology course as important in language learning. These include: concept checking questions (CCQs), flashcards and realia, timelines, contextualisation, focus-on-form, drills, role plays, memory games for revision and consolidation, and the use of pair and group work. The results (Fig.3) showed that for the trainees the most important technique is CCQs, probably because they were new to them, followed by pair and group work. The use of timelines in explaining time-tense relation in teaching grammar, and memory games in consolidating vocabulary, were also considered im-

portant. Less important was the use of flash cards, realia, and role plays. The fact that some of the above activities were not featured in the coursebooks as part of the lesson activities, makes them a second choice, so they were used only if there was time for extra activities at the end of the lesson. Most mentors said they hadn't paid attention to trainees using particular techniques, but were more preoccupied with covering the material in the coursebook – paper or electronic. Of the above techniques the mentors mentioned repetition as being useful in teaching vocabulary to young learners, role plays as 'a modern interactive method', pair and group work as good for practising the language but bad for students' discipline. Some mentors were against trainees using extra activities and ideas which are not part of mentor's teaching repertoire. For the mentors the most important feature of teaching efficiency was covering the material which was assigned to the trainee without leaving out parts of it and without progressing beyond the current lesson in the book.

Fig.3. Activities, techniques and interaction patterns

The fourth area focused on **the language skills**. All present-day courses in second and foreign language teaching have substantial sections dedicated to developing the four language skills, known also as macro skills. The separation of the four skills lies at the core of their research and testing. It is also characteristic of pre-communicative teaching, associated with isolated pattern practice, error avoidance, and native-speaker imitation, and not teaching language as a means of communication (Hinkel 2010). In a lesson the four skills are usually integrated and trainees need to know how to facilitate this integration while still paying attention to the specificities of each skill's development. Within the skills area the study focused on the following sub-areas: pre-, while-, and post-listening/reading; top-down and bottom-up processing of information, student talking time, accuracy and fluency in speaking, process and product writing, and integrating language and skills.

The results (Fig.4) showed that trainees prioritised the clear planning of pre-, while- and post stages in teaching receptive skills, language and skills integration, and the need to increase student talking time which have all been emphasised in the teacher training course. Fluency and accuracy division and top-down

vs. bottom-up processing were considered less significant, probably because trainees found them more abstract. Least important was the process vs. product approaches to writing, bearing in mind that writing is the least practised skill in mainstream classrooms. In the interview most mentors said that the skills development was planned according to the material in the course-book, and the trainees just had to follow the instructions in the teacher's guide. Some mentors mentioned that students should speak more in class, but did not link it to the use any particular technique, such as pair or group work. They also confirmed the importance of fluent and accurate speaking. Only one mentor was familiar with the product and process approach, but said that the students mainly discuss model texts in the course-book, and the writing is usually left for homework. Several mentors agreed that the new language is integrated with skills development, e.g. reading and listening texts are used as context for presenting/integrating language. The mentors did not feel necessary to discuss these aspects of skills development with trainees. They gave them occasional instructions on improving skills development, such as giving instructions, teacher reading the script aloud if students don't understand, or students reading the text in order to concentrate; using a correction code in writing, etc.

Fig.4. Focus on language skills

The last area in the questionnaire was related to **trainees' personal teaching abilities and skills**. The aspects of a teacher's professional expertise which are most relevant to the school-based internship include the ability to plan lessons and courses, to prepare teaching materials and adapt course books to the needs of their students, to manage learners and learning, as well as the ability to use modern technology in the classroom. Therefore, the key aspects focused on in the study included: writing detailed lesson plans, working with the course book, adapting it to the needs of the students, using or designing supplementary activities, looking for online ideas and materials, classroom management, and the use of modern technology.

The results (Fig. 5) indicated that for the trainees the most important teaching abilities were managing students and processes in class, followed by looking for online materials and ideas. Slightly less important were using and designing supplementary activities, and confidently using technology in class. Strictly following the coursebook and writing detailed lesson plans were

not considered essential skills by trainees. However, for the mentors closely following the coursebook was very important. They did not expect trainees to design supplementary materials, as they considered this beyond their expertise. Confident use of technology was considered very important in classes which were taught through technology. This ability depended on the presence of technology in the classroom and the mentor's willingness and skills in using it. Lesson plans were a requirement and the mentors had to check them before each lesson, but they did not expect the trainees to follow them closely and did not discuss changes or deviations from the plan, something that supervisors always discussed with the trainees. Good management skills were not expected from the very beginning of teaching, as mentors thought they develop and become better with time and experience. Some mentors admitted to intervening in the lesson in order to help trainees with technology and in making decisions about teaching in unplanned situations.

Fig.5. Teaching abilities and skills

Conclusion

The findings from the study confirmed that the school-based internship plays a decisive role in shaping the future teachers' views and provides the essential sequence of useful learning experiences which have an impact of trainees' understanding of the profession and potentially affect their professional growth and self-efficacy. Results indicated that the teacher training course has indeed had an important impact on trainees' views, which were not considerably 'shattered' by the clash with the reality of the classroom teaching. In this sense trainees' expectations were met as a whole, although there were areas which gave rise to conflicting priorities with those of their mentors and supervisors.

The results as a whole indicated that the relevance of teaching knowledge, techniques, and ideas is affected by the contexts in which teaching takes place, which, as diverse as they are, bear the features of a local educational tradition characterised by a combination of traditional approaches to teaching (which are slower at embracing new student-centered approaches), and cutting edge teaching material and technologies. Trainees' responses also showed that while they were aware of the value of new ideas, they were still hesitant in their application, and were more likely to opt for safer, established ways of teaching, such as those practised by their mentors.

References:

1. Calderhead, J., Shorrock, S. B. (1997). *Understanding Teacher Education. Case Studies in the Professional Development of Beginning Teachers*. London, Washington D. C.: The Falmer Press.
2. Chamberlin, C. (2000). TESL degree candidates' perceptions of trust in supervisors. *TESOL Quarterly*, 34(4). 653-672.
3. Edge, J. (1992). *Cooperative development*. London: Longman.
4. Freeman, D., Johnson, K. E. (1998). Re-conceptualizing the knowledge-base of language teacher education. *TESOL Quarterly*, 32(3). 397-417.
5. Goldhaber, D., Krieg, J., Theobald, R., & Goggin, M. (2022). Front end to back end: teacher preparation, workforce entry, and attrition. *Journal of Teacher Education*, vol.7, issue 3. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00224871211030303>
6. Hinkel, E. (2010). Integrating the four skills: Current and historical perspectives. In R.B. Kaplan (Ed.), *Oxford Handbook in Applied Linguistics*, (pp. 110-126). 2nd ed. Oxford University Press.
7. Johnson, K. E. (2003). "Every experience is a moving force": Identity and growth through mentoring. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 19. 787-800.
8. Ivanova, I. (2018). The effect of school-based internship for trainees before and after the teacher training course. *Bulgarian English Teachers' Association Newsletter*, 6(30), 147-182. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/323446198>
9. Kumaravadivelu, B. (2006). *Understanding language teaching: From method to postmethod*. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum.
10. Kumaravadivelu, B. (2012). *Language Teacher Education for a Global Society: A Modular Model for Knowing, Analyzing, Recognizing, Doing, and Seeing*. New York: Routledge.
11. Maue, E., Goller, M., Bonnes, K., Karner, T. (2024). Between trust and ambivalence: how does trainee teachers' perception of the relationship with their mentors explain how trainee teachers experience their work? *Vocations and Learning*, 2024, 17, 219-251.
12. Parveen, S., & Mirza, N. (2012). Internship Program in Education: Effectiveness, Problems and Prospects. *International Journal of Learning & Development*, Vol. 2, No. 1, 487-498.
13. Scrivener, J. (2011). *Learning Teaching. The Essential Guide to English Language Teaching* (3rd edition). Oxford: Macmillan.

14. Troman, G. (1996). The rise of the new professionals? The restructuring of primary teachers' work and professionalism. *British Journal of Sociology of Education*, 17(4), 473-487.

15. Tsui, A. (2009). Teaching Expertise: Approaches, Perspectives, and Characterizations. In Burns, A. & Richards, J. (eds.). *The Cambridge Guide to Second Language Teacher Education*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. 190-199